

Farmer Awareness and Management of Aflatoxins in Groundnuts in Western Kenya

Eunice Minyattah-Onyango¹, Noel Makete², Francis O. Wayua^{1*}, Nashon Ambitsi¹, Daniel Chengo³, Eliud Onyango⁴, Lenny Tarus¹, Elkana Nyambati⁵, Giovanna Seddaiu⁶

¹ *Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization, Non-ruminant Research Institute, Kakamega, Kenya*

² *Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization, National Sericulture Research Centre, Thika, Kenya*

³ *Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization, Dairy Research Institute, Naivasha, Kenya*

⁴ *Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization, Food Crops Research Institute, Kabete, Nairobi, Kenya*

⁵ *Kenya Agricultural & Livestock Research Organization, Headquarters, Nairobi, Kenya*

⁶ *Desertification Research Centre, NRD, University of Sassari, Viale Italia 39, 07100, Sassari, Italy*

*Corresponding author: fwayua@yahoo.co.uk; Francis.Obuoro@kalro.org (Tel. +254-710629683)

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ABSTRACT

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is an important food crop in western Kenya, but is highly susceptible to aflatoxin contamination. However, farmer awareness and management strategies of aflatoxins in groundnuts in the region is largely unknown. This study investigated the level of farmer awareness of aflatoxins and its management in groundnuts in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega counties of Kenya. Data was collected through structured interviews with farmers in Bungoma (n=93), Busia (n=83) and Kakamega Counties (n=158). The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square. There were significantly more groundnut farmers in Busia (75%) compared to Kakamega (60%) and Bungoma (50%) (p=0.003). Overall, 66% of farmers were aware of aflatoxin contamination on crops, and 54% had seen aflatoxin on their crops. More farms in Busia county (29%) had detected aflatoxin contamination of their groundnut when compared to Kakamega

(25%) and Bungoma (15%) counties. In the three counties, only about 10% of farmers were aware of Aflasafe KE01, a biocontrol product used in pre-harvest control of aflatoxin in crops. Other pre-harvest management strategies used included selecting the right seed (9%), selecting the right variety (18%), soil fertility management (6%), pest and disease management (24%), weed management (47%), and observing the correct harvesting indices (88%). Postharvest management methods included sun-drying groundnut on bare soil (10%) and tarpaulins (90%), storage of unshelled groundnuts (83%) and shelled groundnuts (18%). This study indicates that the level of farmer awareness and management of aflatoxins in groundnuts in all the study areas was high. However, management strategies did not reflect the effectiveness to prevent and reduce contamination. There is need for capacity building of farmers on identification of symptoms of aflatoxin contamination in groundnuts, predisposing factors and effective postharvest management practices to prevent contamination during storage, marketing and consumption. These interventions will help to reduce the risk of human exposure to aflatoxin contamination. There is need for efficacy trials to extend the usage of Aflasafe KE-01 on groundnuts, which is a crop highly susceptible to contamination by aflatoxins.

Keywords: Groundnut, aflatoxin, awareness, control, farmers, Kenya

1. INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is an important food crop in western Kenya. It is rich in proteins, oil and minerals (Nankya *et al.*, 2021). In western Kenya, it is consumed boiled, roasted, used in relishes served with staple maize porridge commonly known as *ugali*, and also ground to make sauce. Groundnuts are also milled together with other cereals and starches to prepare complementary foods for babies. Small-scale processors process groundnut into peanut butter (Menza *et al.*, 2015). The high nutrient content makes groundnuts highly susceptible to contamination by aflatoxin producing fungi, and this is exacerbated by the humid conditions in the groundnut growing regions. Previous studies have documented aflatoxin contamination of groundnut in western Kenya (Hell and Mutegi, 2011; Ndisio *et al.*, 2017; Menza *et al.*, 2015; Omara *et al.*, 2021).

The worst outbreak of aflatoxin poisoning in the world was reported in Kenya (Omara *et al.*, 2021).

The largest outbreak due to maize aflatoxin poisoning was reported in 2004 where 125 people died

out of the 317 reported cases (Lewis *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, interventions on aflatoxin control in the country have focused more on maize, and the Kenyan community have believed that aflatoxins mainly contaminate maize. Data on awareness of aflatoxin contamination of other crops is scanty. Whereas studies have attempted to document farmer awareness of aflatoxins in other crops such as maize, finger millet and sorghum (Awuor *et al.*, 2021; Ndwiga and Marechera, 2014), studies on farmer awareness of aflatoxins in groundnuts are lacking. This study aimed to document farmer awareness of aflatoxins in groundnuts and its management strategies in Western Kenya. The findings have important implications considering that groundnut is consumed by various population groups, hence the risk of exposure to aflatoxicosis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted in Bungoma, Busia and Kakamega Counties of Western Kenya (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map showing the study areas in Western Kenya

Bungoma County

The County covers an area of 3032.4 km² with an elevation of 1200-4,321 metres above sea level. Main crops produced include maize, beans, groundnuts, finger millet, sweet potatoes, bananas, sorghum, Irish potatoes and assorted vegetables. Sugar cane, cotton, palm oil, coffee, tea, sun flower and tobacco are grown as cash crops in the County (Bungoma CIDP 2018-2022). The EWA-BELT¹ project activities are located in Bumula sub-county in South Bukusu ward (Table 1). This location falls under Upper midland zone (UM).

Busia County

Busia County is situated at the extreme Western region of Kenya and neighboring Uganda. Most parts of Busia County fall within the Lake Victoria Basin. The altitude is undulating and rises from 1,130 metres above sea level at the shores of Lake Victoria to a maximum of about 1,500 metres in the Samia and North Teso Hills. Temperatures range between 21°- 23°C. Relative humidity is fairly high due to the site proximity to Lake Victoria and soils are predominantly nitisols and ferralsols. Crops grown within the county include maize, beans, sweet potatoes, finger millet, cassava, cotton, tobacco and sugar cane (Busia CIDP 2018-2022). The current project activities are located in Nambale sub-county, Bukhayo west ward of Busia county (Table 1). This site is the Lower Midland zone 2 (LM 2).

Kakamega County

Kakamega County is located in western Kenya. The altitude ranges from 1000 m to 2000m above sea level. The county is divided into two main agro-ecological zones, i.e. Upper Midland (UM) and the Lower Midland zone (LM). Farmers in UM practice intensive maize, tea, beans and horticultural

¹ The research presented are part of the EWA-BELT project, which is an European Union funded project which aims at linking East and West African Farming Systems into a BELT of Sustainable Intensification (www.ewabelt.eu)

production. The LM zone includes Butere, Khwisero, Mumias East, Mumias West and Matungu, and the main economic activity is sugar cane production, with some farmers practicing maize, sweet potato, groundnut, finger millet and cassava production (Kakamega CIDP 2018-2022). The project activities are located in Mumias East and Mumias West sub-counties (Table 1) which falls under the lower midland zone.

The three case study areas experience a bimodal rainfall pattern with two distinct crop growing seasons i.e. the long rains season that occurs between March – August and short rains season occurring between September – December followed by a dry spell from December – February.

2.2 Sample size and sampling

The sampling frame consisted of a list of 1,270 farmers from farmers groups working with the EWA-BELT project. The sample size was calculated using the following equation (Yamane, 1967):

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

where n is the suggested sample size, N is the total number of EWA-BELT project farmers in the three study areas and e is the level of precision, set at 5% for the study. Hence the sample size (n) was set at 334 farmers. A proportionate population size (PPS) sampling method was used to allocate the sample size across the study sites (Table 1).

Table 1: Study sites and interviewed respondents in Western Kenya

County	Sub-county	Ward	Number of interviewed respondents			
			Males	Females	Total	Percentage
Bungoma	Bumula	Mateka	10	83	93	27.8
Busia	Nambale	Bukhayo East	17	66	83	24.9
Kakamega	Mumias East	Lusheya-Lubinu	14	50	64	19.2
	Mumias	Musanda	41	53	94	28.1
	West					
Total			82	252	334	100.0

The farmers were randomly selected from the groups. In moving from one randomly selected household to another, the enumerators were guided by village guides, group leaders and agriculture extension officers.

2.3 Data collection

Data was collected using structured questionnaire uploaded on Open Data Kit (ODK) platform. Enumerators were recruited and trained to administer the questionnaire. The data detailed land holdings, land size, crops grown, awareness on aflatoxins and pre- and postharvest groundnut management strategies.

2.4 Data analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, totals and measures of dispersion), continuous and categorical variables being reported as mean±standard deviation and percent, respectively. *Chi-square* test was used to explore associations between variables of interest at 5% level of significance. All analyses were conducted using SPSS (SPSS, 2022). Results are presented in tables, graphs and charts.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic and socio economic characteristics of respondents in the study area

The demographic and characteristics of the farmers are summarized in Table 2. There was a significant difference ($p=0.001$) in the gender of the respondents, where majority of respondents were female (75%). This could be associated with the group approach used by the project since majority of the group members are women. This has significant implication because women play important roles in the groundnut value chain (Onyuka *et al.*, 2016; USAID, 2018). The mean age of the respondents was 48 years. This implies that most of the farmers were advanced in age, indicating

maturity and great potential for increased production. This is consistent with the finding of Onyuka *et al.* (2016) which showed that age of farmers positively influenced groundnut production in Kenya.

Table 2: Demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of respondents in Western Kenya

		Percentage responses (%)				Test statistics (χ^2)
		Bungoma (n=93)	Busia (n=83)	Kakamega (n=158)	Total (n=334)	
Gender of respondents (%)	Female	89.2	79.5	40.9	75.4	0.001
	Male	10.8	20.5	34.8	24.6	
Age of respondent (Years)	Minimum	22	22	20	20	
	Maximum	79	73	82	82	
	Mean	45.9	47.9	49.4	48.4	
	SD*	12.6	12.6	14.3	13.4	
Land size owned (acres)	Minimum	1	1	1	1	
	Maximum	27	12	12	27	
	Mean	2.3	2.8	2.0	2.3	
	SD	2.9	2.2	1.7	2.2	
Land size reserved for crops (acres)	Minimum	1	1	1	1	
	Maximum	10	8	7	10	
	Mean	1.6	2.0	1.4	1.6	
	SD	1.3	1.6	1.0	1.3	

*SD = Standard

Busia County had the largest mean land size per household (2.8 acres) and for cropping (2 acres) while Kakamega County had the least land size (2 acres) and that reserved for cropping (1.4 acres).

This implies that groundnut farming was done in in small-scale. In the region, groundnut is usually grown in the short rains as a rotation of cereals grown in the long rains.

Percentage of farmers growing groundnuts in the three counties

There were significantly more farmers producing groundnut in Busia County ($p=0.003$) compared to Kakamega and Bungoma counties (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Percentage of farmers growing groundnuts in Western Kenya

3.2 Knowledge and awareness of aflatoxins

Two-thirds (66%) of farmers interviewed were aware of aflatoxin contamination on crops and 54% had also seen aflatoxin on their crops. However, there was a significant difference ($p=0.002$) in the percentage of farmers who had observed contamination on their crops in the three counties (

Table 3). Awareness of risk and the potential benefits of solving the problem may influence the choice of corrective strategies, as was found by Mzera (2022), who found that awareness of aflatoxins influences aflatoxin control strategies in Kenya. Findings of the present study differ with those of Awuor *et al.* (2021) in the same region, which reported limited knowledge about aflatoxins, but agree

with the findings of Ndwiga and Marechera (2014) in a study conducted in Eastern Kenya, an area endemic for aflatoxin poisoning.

Table 3: Awareness of aflatoxin by farmers in Western Kenya

Variable	Percentage of farmers (%)				Test statistics		
	Bungoma	Kakamega	Busia	Overall	χ^2	df	p-value
Heard about aflatoxin contamination on crops (Yes)	(n=93)	(n=83)	(n=158)	(n=334)			
	59.1	70.3	66.3	66.2	3.230	2	0.199
Seen/experienced aflatoxin on your crops (Yes)	(n=55)	(n=55)	(n=111)	(n=221)			
	34.5	56.8	67.3	53.8	12.612	2	0.002*
Aware of Aflasafe KE01 (Yes)	(n=55)	(n=55)	(n=111)	(n=221)			
	14.5	12.6	1.8	10.4	5.941	2	0.051*

Busia County had the highest number of farmers (67%) who had experienced aflatoxin contamination on their crops while Bungoma County had the least (35%). This could be mainly because there were more farmers who were planting groundnuts in Busia county as compared to those Bungoma county (Figure 2). Besides, due to proximity to Lake Victoria, most parts of Busia County experience high relative humidity—apt conditions for the growth of aflatoxin-producing fungi. Aflatoxin contamination is a major challenge in groundnut postharvest handling in the region (Awuor *et al.*, 2021; Menza *et al.*, 2015; Onyuka *et al.*, 2016). Conversely, only 10% of farmers were aware of Aflasafe KE01, a biocontrol product used in pre-harvest management of aflatoxin in crops (

Table 3). Aflasafe KE01 is manufactured by KALRO in Katumani but faces distribution challenges to reach farmers. Awareness of Aflasafe KE01 was significantly higher in Bungoma than the other

counties ($p=0.051$), yet Busia county had a significantly higher percentage of farmers experiencing aflatoxin contamination on their crops. This could imply that farmers in Bungoma could have been using Aflasafe KE01 and other aflatoxin control strategies on their crops, hence the lower percentage of farmers experiencing aflatoxins in their crops. This study, however, did not investigate this hypothesis hence this need to be confirmed in future studies.

3.3 Aflatoxin in groundnuts

Overall 24% of the farmers had seen aflatoxin contamination on their groundnut (

Figure 3). Busia had a higher percentage (29%) of farmers who had seen aflatoxin in their groundnut. This could be because more farmers grow groundnut compared to Bungoma and Kakamega counties.

Figure 3: Percentage of farmers who have seen aflatoxin contamination in groundnuts in Western Kenya

Pre-harvest management of aflatoxin in groundnuts

Forty seven percent of the farmers indicated that they conduct weed management while 24% said they conducted pest and disease management on their groundnut farms (

Table 4).

Table 4: Pre-harvest management of groundnuts in Western Kenya

Pre harvest management	Percentage response per County (%)			
	Bungoma (n=46)	Kakamega (n=62)	Busia (n=94)	Total (n=202)
<i>Agronomic activities undertaken (%):</i>				
Selecting the right seed	2.9	5.9	0.0	8.8
Selecting the right variety	0.0	14.7	2.9	17.6
Soil fertility management	0.0	2.9	2.9	5.9
Pest and disease management	5.9	14.7	2.9	23.5

Weed management	11.8	14.7	20.6	47.1
<i>Attributes for checking if groundnut is ready for harvesting (%):</i>				
Browning of leaves	20.8	41.1	26.7	88.6
Random checks by digging	8.9	16.8	12.4	38.1
Length of growth time	3.5	3.0	4.5	10.9
<i>Harvesting method (%):</i>				
Digging using hand hoe	12.9	13.4	13.4	39.6
Uprooting without using hoe or any tool	9.9	33.2	17.3	60.4

Soil fertility and selection of the right variety was not a priority to the farmers. Results of this study also indicated that farmers in the study areas planted only one variety of groundnut—red Valencia. This is a local variety, small and red in colour and preferred roasted. However, this variety is more susceptible to aflatoxin contamination compared to other groundnut varieties (Menza *et al.*, 2015). Data collected on awareness of groundnut maturity indices by farmers revealed that 88% of the farmers checked on the change in colour of the leaves and also conducted random checks by digging the soil (38%) to observe the underground pods. Harvesting of groundnuts in the study areas was mainly done by digging up the plants using hand hoe (40%) and uprooting the whole plant (56%) by hand. Poor pre-harvest and harvest techniques such as late planting, harvesting using hand hoe and premature harvest greatly contribute to aflatoxin contamination in groundnuts (ICRISAT, 2016). The groundnut harvesting methods reported in the present study are similar to those reported in other parts of the country (Ndisio *et al.*, 2017).

Groundnut postharvest management

Ninety percent of the farmers sun-dry the groundnuts on tarpaulin (Table 5). The groundnut was mainly stored in an unshelled state (83%). This has positive postharvest implication as it reduces aflatoxin contamination and enhances shelf-life. Ndisio *et al.* (2017) found that 94% of groundnut samples stored unshelled in Kenya had aflatoxin levels below 10 µg/kg the minimum acceptable

limits set by Kenya’s regulatory authorities (KEBS, 2007). For the farmers who shelled the groundnut, they winnowed and stored without grading and dressing with insecticide. There were various reasons why some groundnut was discarded, these included; small size (37%), deformed nuts (35%), pest and disease damage (35%), immaturity (23%) and mechanical damage (20%). Forty-six percent of the discarded groundnut was fed to poultry and 45% was thrown away. This has implication in terms of risk exposure of consumers to aflatoxin poisoning as previous studies have shown that aflatoxin poisoning can be transmitted through contaminated poultry meat, eggs and other animal products (Adegbeye *et al.*, 2020; Keuchetchatang *et al.*, 2022; Tarus *et al.*, 2018). The groundnut that is thrown away contributes to food loss and waste. While this study did not quantify this, postharvest losses of groundnuts are estimated at 15-35% (Tsusaka *et al.*, 2017; Tibagonzeka *et al.*, 2018). Farmers stored the unshelled groundnut mainly inside the main house (97%) and in ordinary gunny bags (85%). These could increase the chances of aflatoxin contamination since aeration in the main house may not be conducive for storage of groundnuts. Previous studies show that conditions such as excessive heat, high humidity, lack of aeration in stores, and insect and rodent damage provide favorable conditions for growth of fungus (Hell and Mutegi, 2011; ICRISAT, 2016).

Table 5: Postharvest management practices of groundnuts in western Kenya

Post-harvest management	Percent responses (%)			
	Bungoma (n=45)	Kakamega (n=62)	Busia (n=95)	Total (n=202)
<i>Drying methods used (%)</i>				
Sun drying on bare soil	3.5	5.0	2.0	10.4
Sun drying on tarpaulins	19.8	41.1	29.2	90.1
Solar drying	0	0	0	0
<i>Storage state (%)</i>				
Shelled groundnut	5.0	7.9	5.0	17.8
Unshelled	19.3	38.1	25.7	83.2
Groundnut flour	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.5
<i>Threshing method (%)</i>				

Hitting bagged groundnut with sticks	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.5
Hitting harvested groundnut on tarpaulin	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0
Mechanical thresher	0	0	0	0
Threshing of pods using bare hands and fingers	22.8	46.0	30.2	99.0
<i>Handling threshed groundnut (%)</i>				
Winnow and store	16.8	32.2	18.3	67.3
Winnow, grade and store	5.0	8.9	4.0	17.8
<i>Storage method for harvested groundnuts (%)</i>				
Normal gunny bags	21.3	38.1	26.2	85.6
Silos	0	0	0	0
Storage bin	0.0	2.0	1.0	3.0
Storage pots	0.0	1.5	2.0	3.5
Hermetic bags	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.5

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study reveals that the level of farmer awareness and management of aflatoxins in groundnuts in all the three study areas was high. However, management options did not reflect the use of effective control measures. There is need for introduction of improved groundnut varieties with less resistance to aflatoxin contamination, but still with consumer preferred and desired attributes. Whereas Aflasafe KE-01 has been licensed as a biocontrol agent to control aflatoxin contamination of maize, and has proven to be effective in pre-harvest control of aflatoxin contamination of harvested maize, there is need for efficacy trials to extend the usage of the product on groundnuts, which is a crop highly susceptible to contamination with aflatoxins. On-postharvest interventions, there is need for capacity building of farmers on identification of symptoms of aflatoxin contaminated groundnuts, pre-disposing factors and effective postharvest management practices to prevent contamination during storage, marketing and consumption. There is also need for awareness creation on the implications of feeding aflatoxin-contaminated groundnuts to livestock. These interventions are particularly

important considering that groundnut is consumed by a large proportion of the population in the study areas, hence this will reduce the risk of exposure to aflatoxin contamination.

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